

Studies on Sulphonylhydrazones : Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of Arylsulphonyl-(4-substituted)-aceto/propiofenonehydrazones

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Some new arylsulphonylhydrazones have been prepared by condensation of *p*-chloroacetophenone, *p*-methylpropiofenone and *p*-bromopropiofenone and 4-arylsulphonamidoacetophenone with different arylsulphonylhydrazines. The products were tested for antimicrobial activity. The constitution was supported by ir spectra.

SULPHONYLHYDRAZINE derivatives possess wide therapeutic activity, viz. antibacterial¹, fungicidal² and antituberculostatic³ activity. Sulphonamides⁴ showed antibacterial, anticancer, anticonvulsant, antimalarial and antifungal activities. *p*-Aminoacetophenone has the same bactericidal effect as sulphonamides⁵. With a view to get better therapeutic agents, we have prepared different arylsulphonyl-(4-chloro/bromo/methyl)-aceto/propiofenonehydrazones (I) by the condensation of *p*-chloroacetophenone, *p*-methyl propiofenone and *p*-bromopropiofenone with different sulphonylhydrazines. The sulphonylhydrazines were synthesised by condensing different arylsulphonylchloride and hydrazine hydrate⁶.

Y = Cl, CH₃, Br; X = CH₃, C₂H₅; R = Aryl

R = Aryl

Arylsulphonylhydrazones of the type II were also prepared by condensing 4-arylsulphonamido acetophenone with different arylsulphonyl hydrazines. The constitution of the products were supported by ir spectra⁷. The products were screened for antibacterial activity.

The ir spectra (KBr) of phenylsulphonyl-4-bromopropiofenone hydrazone (I) showed bands at 3220 (NH stretching) and 1320 cm⁻¹ (SO₂), and those of phenylsulphonyl-(4-sulphonamido)-acetophenonehydrazone showed bands at 3220 (NH stretching), 1320 (S-O) and 1160 cm⁻¹ (SO₂NH).

Experimental

Preparation of arylsulphonyl-(4-chloroacetophenonehydrazone): The phenylsulphonylhydrazine (0.01 mol) was dissolved in hot methanol (25 ml) containing a little water. *p*-Chloroacetophenone (0.01 mol) was then added dropwise with stirring. The crystals were separated from the reaction mixture after 2 h at room temperature. The product was filtered and crystallised from methanol. Similarly other products were prepared by condensing different arylsulphonylhydrazines with *p*-bromoacetophenone, *p*-methylacetophenone, *p*-toluenesulphonamidoacetophenone and *p*-benzenesulphonamidoacetophenone.

Antibacterial activity: The compounds were tested for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* by cup-plate method⁸ using ethanol as solvent. When R = phenyl and *p*-chlorophenyl, X = ethyl, Y = bromo of type I, they were highly active (zone of inhibition = 40-44 mm) against *S. aureus*; and when R = *p*-anisyl, phenyl and *p*-bromophenyl, X = ethyl, Y = bromomethyl of type I they were highly active (zone of inhibition = 30 mm) against *E. coli*. When R = *p*-chlorophenyl, R' = *p*-chlorophenyl and *p*-tolyl of type II they were highly active (zone of inhibition = 40 mm) against *S. aureus*. Other products of type I and II were moderately active against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* (zone of inhibition = 10 to 30 mm).

TABLE I—ARYLSULPHONYL-(4-SUBSTITUTED)-ACETO/PROPIOFENONE HYDRAZONES

Sl. no.	R	X	Y	M.p. °C	Yield %	N% Found (Calcd.)
1.	Phenyl	Methyl	Chloro	172-73	60	9.0 (9.08)
2.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Methyl	Chloro	166-67	71	8.2 (8.16)
3.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Methyl	Chloro	155-56	70	8.4 (8.66)
4.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	Methyl	Chloro	140-42	68	7.0 (7.23)

(Table 1 contd.)

5.	Acetamidophenyl	Methyl	Chloro	162-63	62	11.20 (11.49)
6.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	Methyl	Chloro	180-82	72	8.50 (8.83)
7.	Anisyl	Methyl	Chloro	132-34	74	8.0 (8.27)
8.	Phenyl	Ethyl	Bromo	167-69	65	7.75 (7.63)
9.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Ethyl	Bromo	145-47	64	6.8 (6.97)
10.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Ethyl	Bromo	166-68	66	7.5 (7.34)
11.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	Ethyl	Bromo	144-46	69	6.35 (6.27)
12.	Acetamidophenyl	Ethyl	Bromo	162-64	58	9.8 (9.9)
13.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	Ethyl	Bromo	195-96	63	7.5 (7.31)
14.	Anisyl	Ethyl	Bromo	130-32	61	7.15 (7.05)
15.	Phenyl	Ethyl	Methyl	172-74	70	9.3 (9.27)
16.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Ethyl	Methyl	166-68	72	9.45 (8.32)
17.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Ethyl	Methyl	155-57	71	8.95 (8.85)
18.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	Ethyl	Methyl	140-42	72	7.52 (7.34)
19.	Acetamidophenyl	Ethyl	Methyl	162-63	70	11.78 (11.69)
20.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	Ethyl	Methyl	80-82	64	8.70 (8.8)
21.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Ethyl	Methyl	132-34	64	8.40 (8.86)

Compd. no. 1 gave satisfactory C, H analyses ; all compounds gave satisfactory N analyses.

(Table 2 contd.)

6.	Phenyl	<i>m</i> -Carboxyphenyl	152-55	80	8.7 (8.88)
7.	Phenyl	2-Hydroxy-3-Carboxyphenyl	122-24	80	8.6 (8.58)
8.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Phenyl	140-42	86	8.5 (9.48)
9.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Bromophenyl	149-51	80	8.0 (8.04)
10.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	180-82	77	8.9 (8.79)
11.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	95-97	76	9.25 (9.19)
12.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Naphthyl	152-53	73	8.84 (8.52)
13.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	<i>m</i> -Carboxyphenyl	145-46	81	8.8 (8.62)
14.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	2-Hydroxy-3-carboxyphenyl	130-32	83	8.20 (8.34)
15.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Phenyl	146-48	85	9.0 (9.06)
16.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Bromophenyl	120-22	81	7.6 (7.74)
17.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	102-04	82	8.75 (8.43)
18.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	162-64	77	8.9 (8.80)
19.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Naphthyl	160-61	79	8.5 (8.18)
20.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	<i>m</i> -Carboxyphenyl	108-10	81	8.3 (8.5)
21.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	2-Hydroxy-3-carboxyphenyl	120-21	81	8.00 (8.02)

Compd. no. 1 gave satisfactory C, H analyses ; all compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

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TABLE 2—ARYLSULPHONYL-(4-SULPHONAMIDO)-ACETOPHENONE HYDRAZONES

Sl. no.	R	R'	M.p. °C	Yield %	N% Found/Calcd.
1.	Phenyl	Phenyl	168-69	82	9.8 (9.79)
2.	Phenyl	Bromophenyl	180-81	73	8.8 (8.26)
3.	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	110-11	71	9.10 (9.06)
4.	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	130-32	81	9.5 (9.48)
5.	Phenyl	Naphthyl	105-7	67	8.8 (8.77)